

ISic3465

I.Sicily inscription 3465

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Gaulus

Place of origin (modern)

Gozo

Provenance

Victoria, found near the gate of the Castle, on the bridge

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Victoria, Gozo, Museo archeologico nazionale (Cittadella)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR113413

1. [L] (ucio) Cestio L (uci) f (ilio) Pompt (ina) Gallo Va
2. reniãño Lutaãño Natali Aem [i]
3. liãño patãfono minikipi municipi
4. [T]i (berius) Mãrcius Mãrciãanusãmico opãtm [o]
5. êt karissimo carissimo sãibi honoris câusa s (tatuam) p(osuit).

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285155

EDR 113413

EDCS 22100625

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7506 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bruno, B. 2004. L'arcipelago maltese in età romana e bizantina. Attività economiche e scambi al centro del Mediterraneo. Bari. At 58

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3465. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388616>